

E.FACTORY

Energy.Factory is an offer targeted at students in the 7th and 8th grade. It aims to spark enthusiasm for the energy transition and trigger interest in professions related to this field.

WHAT IS E.FACTORY ABOUT?

The main element of our offer for schools is a virtual factory that presents the processes of a chocolate factory in the format of a computer game and addresses the energy system in a playful manner.

Two explanatory videos guide the students through the game.

HOW DOES THE INTERACTION WORK?

The students can change setting parameters in the factory and observe the effects on the quality of the chocolate produced, the energy consumption and the factory's CO₂ emissions.

In small groups, students optimise the individual steps with the aim of achieving a high quality chocolate with low CO₂ emissions.

WHO IS E.FACTORY ADDRESSED TO?

Are you a teacher or director of a secondary school and would like to spark enthusiasm for the energy transition in your students?

This offer is available in Upper Austria (OÖ Energiesparverband).

Our contact details:
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www.vorzeigeregion-energie.at

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